

A Chiral Propeller-Shaped Triple Helicene Shows Multi-Resonant Thermally Activated Delayed Fluorescence

Jingxiang Wang,^a Jhon Sebastian Oviedo Ortiz,^b Aidan P. McKay,^a David B. Cordes,^a Jeanne Crassous,^b and Eli Zysman-Colman^{*a}

^a Organic Semiconductor Centre, EaStCHEM School of Chemistry, University of St Andrews, St Andrews, Fife, UK, KY16 9ST

Fax: +44-1334 463808; Tel: +44-1334 463826, e-mail: eli.zysman-colman@st-andrews.ac.uk

^b University of Rennes, CNRS, ISCR (Institut des Sciences Chimiques de Rennes) – UMR 6226, F-35000 Rennes, France

Dedicated to Prof. *Marcel Mayor* on the occasion of his 60th birthday.

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Multi-resonant thermally activated delayed fluorescence (MR-TADF) helicenes show great potential as chiral emitters due to their typically high photoluminescence quantum yield and that they emit circularly polarized luminescence. Here, a new propeller-shaped chiral MR-TADF helicene **DiKTa3**, integrating three **DiKTa** moieties, was designed and synthesized aiming to achieve co-parallel electronic and magnitude transition dipole moments that would lead to a high dissymmetry factor, g . It emits at λ_{PL} of 491 nm, with a full width at half maximum of 52 nm and has a moderate ΔE_{ST} value of 0.24 eV in toluene. The separated (*P,P,P*) enantiomer shows an absorption dissymmetry factor $|g_{\text{abs}}|$ of 6.8×10^{-4} at 450 nm, which results from a lower symmetry conformation adopted by the compound in solution than the C_3 -symmetric optimized structure. This work highlights the strong influence that geometry can have on the chiroptical properties of the emitter.

Keywords: Chirality, helicene, circular dichroism, circularly polarized luminescence, multi-resonant thermally activated delayed fluorescence.

Introduction

Many chiral helicenes show interesting chiroptical properties and these materials have been widely investigated in such diverse fields as bioimaging, optical data storage, optical spintronics applications, and circularly polarized organic light-emitting diodes (CP-OLEDs).^[1–8] Most emissive chiral helicenes are fluorescent, but for efficient OLEDs, triplet excitons need to be harvested, so helicenes that emit either phosphorescence or thermally activated delayed fluorescence (TADF) would be potentially attractive emitters. Organic multi-resonant TADF (MR-TADF)

materials have attracted particular attention as emitters for OLEDs as not only can devices attain 100% internal quantum efficiency (IQE) but they also show narrowband emission and high photoluminescence quantum yield (Φ_{PL}).^[9–12] Thus, the development of chiral MR-TADF emitters would be particularly attractive for CP-MR-TADF OLEDs.

The extent of electronic circular dichroism (ECD) and circularly polarized luminescence (CPL) from chiral emitters can be quantified by the absorption and luminescence dissymmetry factors, g_{abs} and g_{PL} , which are defined by equation 1 and 2, respectively:

$$g_{\text{abs}} = 2 \frac{(\varepsilon_L - \varepsilon_R)}{(\varepsilon_L + \varepsilon_R)} \quad (1)$$

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$$g_{\text{PL}} = 2 \frac{(I_L - I_R)}{(I_L + I_R)} \quad (2)$$

where ε_L and ε_R are the molar absorptivity coefficients associated with left- and right-handed circularly polarized light, respectively. I_L and I_R correspond to the intensities of the emitted left- and right-handed light, respectively. g_{PL} values of -2 or 2 indicate 100% right- or left-handed CPL. As the CPL is related to the transition between excited states and ground state of the emitter, the g_{PL} of a chiral molecule is dependent on the magnitude of the magnetic and electric transition dipole moments and their relative orientation according to equation 3:

$$g_{\text{PL}} = \frac{4|\boldsymbol{\mu}||\mathbf{m}|}{|\boldsymbol{\mu}|^2 + |\mathbf{m}|^2} \cos\theta \quad (3)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and \mathbf{m} refer to the electric transition dipole moment and magnetic transition dipole moment vectors between the emissive excited state and the ground state, respectively, and θ is the angle between $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and \mathbf{m} .^[13,14] For closed shell organic small molecules, including MR-TADF emitters, $|\boldsymbol{\mu}|$ is roughly 300 times larger than $|\mathbf{m}|$, which results in very small g_{PL} values, typically less than 10^{-2} .^[13] Given the large electric transition dipole moment, equation 3 can be simplified to equation 4:

$$g_{\text{PL}} \approx \frac{4|\mathbf{m}|}{|\boldsymbol{\mu}|} \cos\theta \quad (4)$$

It therefore becomes clear that to enhance g_{PL} requires a combination of higher $|\mathbf{m}|$ and lower $|\boldsymbol{\mu}|$ and a parallel arrangement between them. Unfortunately, the planar geometries of most MR-TADF materials, including MR-TADF helicenes, result in a nearly perpendicular arrangements between \mathbf{m} and $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ (Figure 1), which result in low absolute values of $\cos\theta$ and low g_{PL} values of $< 3 \times 10^{-3}$ (Figure S24).^[15–24] However, if two identical MR-TADF helicenes are fused into one C_2 -symmetric dimer molecule, the integrated $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and \mathbf{m} of the dimeric emitter would be parallel or anti-parallel to each other (Figure 1).^[25–28] A large $\cos\theta$ value of 1 would certainly contribute to a higher g_{PL} value. Based on this strategy, in particular, Guo *et al.* developed **BN[9]H**, which has the highest $|g_{\text{PL}}|$ value of 5.8×10^{-3} in toluene among all the reported chiral MR-TADF helicenes (Figure 1).^[28] The CP-OLEDs with **P-BN[9]H** achieved both high EQE_{max} of 35.4% and

electroluminescence dissymmetry factor, g_{EL} , value of 6.2×10^{-3} .

With the goal of increasing g_{PL} , we designed a C_3 -symmetric MR-TADF helicene **DiKta3** (Figure 2) that we calculated to have co-parallel $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and \mathbf{m} and thus a high predicted g_{PL} value. **DiKta3** emits at λ_{PL} of 491 nm (FWHM of 52 nm/0.26 eV) and has a moderate ΔE_{ST} value of 0.24 eV in toluene and is very poorly emissive. The 1 wt% doped film of **DiKta3** in PMMA exhibits TADF. The density functional theory calculated (M062X/6-31G(d,p))^[29,30] chiroptical properties based on the optimized geometry predict g_{abs} values of 2.1×10^{-2} for the S_0 – S_1 transition due to a $\cos\theta$ value of 1. However, the predicted value differs considerable from the measured one in toluene (g_{abs} of 6.8×10^{-4}). This is the result of **DiKta3** adopting a conformation that is not C_3 -symmetric; indeed, the calculated g_{abs} value using geometry obtained from the single crystal structure is 8.1×10^{-4} . This work demonstrates how a small change in the geometry of a helicene results in a large difference in the transition dipole moments and the corresponding g_{abs} value. These results may also explain why many triple helicenes show low g_{abs} values of around 10^{-3} .^[31]

Results & Discussion

Synthesis

The synthesis of **DiKta3** is shown in Figure 2a. The intermediate **1** was prepared through a palladium-catalyzed Buchwald-Hartwig amination between 1,3,5-tribromobenzene and aniline in 72% yield, which was then reacted with dimethyl 2-bromoisophthalate through an Ullmann coupling reaction to afford **2** in 68% yield. Then intermediate **2** was hydrolyzed to the acid, activated using thionyl chloride, which then cyclized via Friedel-Crafts acylation to afford **DiKta3** in a yield of 8%. The identity and purity of **DiKta3** and the intermediates were determined by melting point analysis, ^1H and ^{13}C nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS), high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), and elemental analysis (EA) (Figure S1–S15). The structure of **DiKta3** was confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction (Figure 2b) with X-ray quality crystals obtained from slow evaporation of a THF:MeOH solution. The compound crystallizes as a mixture of (*P,P,P*)- and (*M,M,M*)-enantiomers. The conformation distorts away from planarity due to the large steric hindrance between the three **DiKta** blades, which results in a propeller-shaped triple

Monomer MR-TADF helicenes:

Dimer MR-TADF helicenes:

This work (Trimer MR-TADF helicene):

Proposed parallel μ and m

Figure 1. Structures and calculated angle θ between transition dipole moments of examples of monomer and dimer MR-TADF helicenes and molecular design of DiKTa3.

Figure 2. (a) Synthesis scheme of **DiKta3**. (b) Face and side-on thermal ellipsoid plots of the structure of **DiKta3**. Ellipsoids are displayed at the 50% probability level, hydrogens are omitted for clarity.

helicene with similar torsion angles C6–C1–N1–C16, C4–C5–N5–C44 and C2–C3–N3–C30 of 38.4(7), 35.7(8) and 42.8(8)°, respectively. The **DiKta** blades are also bent along their length with the angle between the two C₆ rings of each arm being 16.1(2), 17.2(3), and 22.7(3)°.

Theoretical Calculations

The optimized geometry of the ground state and its electronic structure of **DiKta3** were calculated using Density Functional Theory (DFT) at the PBE0/6-31G(d,p) level, starting from a structure drawn and optimized using Chem3D (Figure 3a).^[30,32] The highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) of **DiKta3** is located on two of the DiKta blades while the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) is distributed across the whole molecule. The calculated HOMO and LUMO energies of **DiKta3** are –6.42/–2.72 eV. Both orbitals are more stabilized than the parent **DiKta** (HOMO of –6.20 and LUMO of –2.23 eV) and the double helicene **Hel-DiDiKta** (HOMO of –6.26 and LUMO of –2.53 eV).^[17,33] The excited-state energies were calculated using time-dependent DFT (TD-DFT) within the Tamm-Dancoff approximation (TDA) at the PBE0/6-31G(d,p) level. The S₁ and T₁ energies of **DiKta3** are calculated to be 2.85/2.43 eV, with ΔE_{ST} of 0.42 eV. There are six triplet states below the S₁ state,

which may participate in the RISC process.^[34–36] The SOC matrix elements (SOCME) between S₁ and T₁ to T₆ transitions are calculated to be 4.20, 1.74, 1.15, 1.46, 2.10 and 1.73 cm^{–1}, based on the optimized T₁ geometry, respectively (Figure 3a). These values are close to those of the parent **DiKta** (1.26, 6.66, 9.34 and 6.84 cm^{–1} for S₁–T₁, S₁–T₂, S₁–T₃ and S₁–T₄ transitions, respectively, Figure S16). It is known that TD-DFT calculations overestimate ΔE_{ST}, and so spin-component scaling second-order algebraic diagrammatic construction (SCS-(ADC)2/cc-pVDZ) calculations were undertaken as these account for higher order electronic excitations.^[37,38] As shown in Figure 3b, **DiKta3** shows short range charge transfer (SRCT) character with the typical alternating increasing and decreasing electron density pattern on the center of the molecule for both S₁ and T₁. The S₁ and T₁ energies of 2.72 and 2.58 eV are much more stabilized compared to those of **DiKta** (S₁ = 3.46 eV and T₁ = 3.20 eV).^[39] The corresponding ΔE_{ST} value is calculated to be 0.14 eV.

Optoelectronic Properties

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) and differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) of **DiKta3** in degassed DCM with 0.1 M [t-Bu₄N]PF₆ as the supporting electrolyte and Fc/Fc⁺ as the internal reference (0.46 V vs. SCE)^[40] were meas-

Figure 3. (a) Calculated electron density distribution (isovalue: 0.02) of the HOMO, LUMO and energy levels in the gas phase based on optimized ground-state geometry and SOCME based on optimized T_1 geometry at the PBE0/6-31G(d,p) level. (b) Difference density plots and energies of S_1 and T_1 calculated in the gas phase at SCS-(ADC)2/cc-pVDZ level (Blue indicates an area of decreased electron density while yellow indicates increased electronic density between the ground and excited states).

ured to experimentally determine the HOMO and LUMO energy levels (Figure S17). **DiKTa3** shows a reversible reduction wave and an irreversible oxidation wave, electrochemical behavior that is consistent with that of **DiKTa**.^[33] The reduction potential, E_{red} , and oxidation potential, E_{ox} , of **DiKTa3**, obtained from the peak values in the DPV are -1.02 and 1.83 V vs. SCE. Both values are cathodically shifted compared to **DiKTa** (E_{red} of -1.34 V and E_{ox} of 1.78 V vs. SCE)^[33] and

closer to those of **Hel-DiDiKTa** (E_{red} of -1.16 V and E_{ox} of 1.81 V vs. SCE).^[17] The corresponding HOMO and LUMO energies are -6.17 and -3.32 eV with energy gap ΔE of 2.85 eV (Table S1).

The ultraviolet-visible (UV-vis) absorption and photoluminescence (PL) spectra of **DiKTa3** in toluene at room temperature are shown in Figure 4a. The lowest-energy absorption band is at 450 nm and has a molar absorptivity of 1.6×10^4 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹, values that resemble

Figure 4. (a) UV-vis absorption and PL spectra of **DiKTa3** in toluene at 300 K; Inset: photo of **DiKTa3** in toluene excited at 365 nm. (b) PL spectra of **DiKTa3** in different solvents at 300 K. ($\lambda_{exc} = 430$ nm).

those of **Hel-DiDiKTa** (453 nm, $1.4 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)^[17] and can be assigned to the S_0 – S_1 transition. The red-shifted band and lower molar absorptivity compared to that in **DiKTa** (433 nm, $2.1 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)^[33] align with the trends of the calculated oscillator strength and energy of the S_0 – S_1 transition (2.72 eV and 0.0016 for **DiKTa3** and 3.46 eV and 0.20 for **DiKTa**).^[39] **DiKTa3** emits at λ_{PL} of 491 nm, shows narrowband emission, with a FWHM of 52 nm/0.26 eV, and has a small Stokes shift of 38 nm/0.21 eV in toluene. Its emission is red-shifted compared to **DiKTa** (453 nm) and **Hel-DiDiKTa** (473 nm).^[17] The shoulder emission band peaking at 515 nm and the higher-intensity absorption band at 429 nm ($2.4 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) may come from the transitions between different vibrational energy levels as the PL spectra remain unchanged as a function of changing excitation wavelengths between 405–455 nm (Figure S18). In addition, the energy of the emission band is insensitive to solvent polarity, which indicates that its SRCT state has significant locally-excited character (Figure 4b). The Φ_{PL} of **DiKTa3** in degassed toluene is measured to be 0.4%, the magnitude of which is mainly due to the significant non-radiative decay. This low Φ_{PL} value is perhaps not

surprising as that of **Hel-DiDiKTa** is also $\approx 1\%$ ^[17] and such low Φ_{PL} is not uncommon in triple-helicene compounds.^[31]

The steady-state PL (SS PL) and phosphorescence (Ph) spectra of **DiKTa3** at 77 K were measured in toluene and are shown in Figure 5a–5b. Due to its low Φ_{PL} , the SS PL at 77 K is dominated by the phosphorescence. The singlet and triplet energies, determined from the onsets of the SS PL and Ph spectra, are 2.61 and 2.37 eV. The corresponding ΔE_{ST} value is 0.24 eV, which is slightly larger than the calculation result (0.14 eV) and similar to that of single **DiKTa** (0.20 eV).^[41] The time-resolved PL decay in degassed toluene is shown in Figure 5c. The prompt emission of **DiKTa3** decays with lifetime τ_{PL} of 6.7 ns. No delayed emission was observed in solution because of the low Φ_{PL} , large ΔE_{ST} , and significant non-radiative decay.^[42]

The photophysical properties of **DiKTa3** in doped polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) films were then investigated. The Φ_{PL} remains very low at 0.6% in 1 wt % doped film. **DiKTa3** emits at λ_{PL} of 492 nm with FWHM of 54 nm/0.26 eV at 300 K (Figure 6a). The S_1 , T_1 energies and ΔE_{ST} value in film, determined from the SS PL and Ph spectra at 77 K, are 2.64, 2.41 eV and

Figure 5. (a) Steady-state PL and phosphorescence spectra of **DiKTa3** in toluene at 77 K. (b) The fluorescence band of **DiKTa3** in toluene at 77 K. ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 430 \text{ nm}$) (c) Time-resolved PL decay of **DiKTa3** in degassed toluene ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 375 \text{ nm}$).

Figure 6. (a) Steady-state PL spectra at 300 K ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 415 \text{ nm}$). (b) PL decay of the prompt component at 300 K ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 375 \text{ nm}$). (c) Variable temperature time-resolved PL spectra in 1 wt% doped film in PMMA ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 375 \text{ nm}$).

0.23 eV (Figure S19), which are close to those measured in toluene. The prompt emission decays with a τ_{PL} of 4.0 ns (Figure 6b). There is a weak observed delayed emission, with a lifetime, τ_{d} , of 487 ns (Figure 6c). This delayed emission increases in intensity with increasing temperature, thus we can assign this to TADF.

Recognizing that **DiKta3** is chiral, we next investigated its chiroptical properties. The enantiomers of the racemic sample of **DiKta3** were firstly separated by chiral HPLC to afford ee. of 100% and 99.6% for the first and the second enantiomers, respectively (Figure S14–S15). The racemization barrier of **DiKta3** was firstly calculated at the M062X/6-31G(d,p) level of theory (Figure S20). There are three helical moieties in **DiKta3**, resulting in three transition states with racemization barriers of $\Delta G^\ddagger = 33.9$, 36.8, 33.9 kcal mol⁻¹ from (P,P,P)- to (P,P,M)-, (P,M,M)- and (M,M,M)-**DiKta3**, respectively. The calculated high energy barriers enable the chiral separation of **DiKta3**. The simulated ECD spectra of (P,P,P)-**DiKta3** in toluene based on PBE0/6-31G(d,p)^[30] and M062X/6-31G(d,p)^[29] calculations were employed to be able to assign the absolute configuration by comparison with the measured ECD spectra (Figure S21). Both simulated ECD spectra of (P,P,P)-**DiKta3** show positive signals for the low-energy absorption bands and the M062X/6-31G(d,p) calculations gave simulated spectra that are more consistent with the experimental spectra (Figure 7). (P,P,P)- and (M,M,M)-**DiKta3** display mirror image ECD spectra. However, the absorption dissymmetry factor g_{abs} values of the lowest-energy absorption band at 450 nm are unexpectedly very low at $+6.8 \times 10^{-4}$ and -7.5×10^{-4} for (P,P,P)/(M,M,M)-**DiKta3**, respectively. CPL spectra of (P,P,P)/(M,M,M)-**DiKta3** in toluene were also measured (Figure S22) with low g_{PL}

signals. Due to its weak Φ_{PL} , we are not able to extract accurate g_{PL} values.

To explore the origin of the low g_{abs} values, TDA-DFT calculations at the PBE0/6-31G(d,p) and M062X/6-31G(d,p) levels starting from the optimized ground-state geometries of (P,P,P)-**DiKta3** were firstly performed to predict the g_{abs} values in toluene (Figure 8a–8b). The geometries optimized by both methods are C₃-symmetric triple helicenes with the same three torsion angles (C6–C1–N1–C16, C4–C5–N5–C44 and C2–C3–N3–C30) of 38.9, 38.8, 38.8° and 39.4, 39.5, 39.4° for each functional, respectively (Figure S23). They give similar predicted magnetic transition dipole moment values $|m|$, small θ of 33 and 3° and high $\cos\theta$ of 0.84 and 1, respectively. The computed electric transition dipole moment values $|\mu|$ are higher using M062X/6-31G(d,p), which leads to a lower calculated g_{abs} value of 2.1×10^{-2} compared to that of PBE0 (5.6×10^{-1}). However, both predicted values are vastly overestimated compared to the experimental result in toluene. This is likely due to the differences between the near-identical optimized torsion angles and those observed in the single crystal structure (38.4, 35.7 and 42.8°, Figure 2). Therefore, the chiroptical properties of (P,P,P)-**DiKta3** were also calculated using the crystal structure geometry at the M062X/6-31G(d,p) level for comparison (Figure 8c). The calculated $|m|$ is close to the calculations based on the optimized geometries. However, the differences between the three torsion angles breaks the symmetry of the molecule, resulting in an increased $|\mu|$ and smaller $\cos\theta$ of 0.38. The corresponding g_{abs} value is calculated to be 8.1×10^{-4} , which is much closer to the value measured in toluene for the compound (6.8×10^{-4}). These results indicate

Figure 7. (a) ECD spectra and (b) g_{abs} values of **DiKta3** recorded in toluene solution.

Figure 8. Density plot of the NTO [hole (blue) & electron (red)] of the S_1 state and calculated chiroptical properties of (P,P,P) -**DiKta3** at the optimized ground-state geometries based on (a) PBE0/6-31G(d,p) and (b) M062X/6-31G(d,p) calculations and (c) at the chiroptical properties at the M062X/6-31G(d,p) level based on the geometry from the crystal structure.

that a slight change in conformation leads to a large difference in the predicted chiroptical properties.

Conclusions

A new chiral MR-TADF triple helicene **DiKta3** was designed to have high g_{PL} wherein the electronic and magnitude transition dipole moments would align in a co-parallel fashion. The SCS-(ADC)2 calculations and the photophysics point to a compound that is poorly luminescent, although is MR-TADF. The electric and magnetic transition dipole moments of (P,P,P) -**DiKta3** calculated based on the optimized geometries show almost co-parallel arrangements, which result in large calculated $|g_{\text{abs}}|$ of $> 10^{-2}$. However, the calculations based on the crystal structure geometry, which adopts a lower symmetry, show much different results where there is an angle of 67° between the electric and magnetic transition dipole moments and a much lower g_{abs} of 8.1×10^{-4} , a value that aligns with the measured g_{abs} of 6.8×10^{-4} in toluene. This result illustrates that the geometry of **DiKta3** in toluene may be closer to that of the crystal structure rather than the perfectly C_3 -symmetric optimized geometries from DFT calculations. This small difference on geometries finally results in large difference in the transition dipole moments and the g value.

Supporting Information

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra, HRMS, HPLC and EA of all target compounds; X-ray crystallographic detail; supplementary computational data; photophysical data.^[13,17,29,30,32,33,40,43–70]

Author Contribution Statement

Jingxiang Wang, conceived the molecular design, performed the synthesis, the theoretical calculations, and the optoelectronic characterization. The crystal structures were determined by Dr. Aidan P. McKay and Dr. David B. Cordes. The chiroptical properties were measured by Jhon Sebastian Oviedo Ortiz. Dr. Jeanne Crassous and Prof. Eli Zysman-Colman supervised the project. All authors contributed to the manuscript.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The research data supporting this publication can be accessed at <https://doi.org/10.17630/a3917a0d-9839-4465-8c51-f89d4a0fd44d>. Deposition Number <https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/services/structures?id=doi:10.1002/hlca.202400129>, CCDC 2376257 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/structures.

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